

Portable Energy Harvester between Ambient Air and Soil

(Penuai Tenaga Haba Mudah Alih antara Udara Ambien dan Tanah)

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ABSTRACT

Wireless sensors networks (WSNs) has become a popular topic over the years due to its vast application in various fields such as health, automation, security and many more. However, WSNs particularly in remote areas where their use is most advantageous, is hindered by the major challenge of limited energy, which is battery powered. Alternatives have been researched to overcome this challenge and one such solution is energy harvesting using thermal energy. Thermal energy is an abundant supply and can be found anywhere. Hence, this paper proposes a concept utilizing a thermoelectric device to convert thermal energy into electrical power, as well as a feasibility study whether a WSN could be supplied by this approach. The study area coverage is at the lake nearby Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment (FKAB). The temperature profile of the soil of various depth has been studied to find the optimum depth for maximum temperature differences between ambient air and in the soil. Using the data collected, the efficiency of thermoelectric generator (TEG) with different configurations is tested in the lab. Then, energy storage devices and buck-booster are used to further enhance the capabilities of TEG. All the models are then integrated and tested to power up electronics load according to the temperature profile collected. Arduino Uno was used as load and it was successfully powered up for a short duration of time before energy fully depleted. In short, thermal energy harvesting can power up WSNs, however not efficient enough to be stand-alone power source.

Keywords: Thermal energy harvesting; Wireless sensor nodes (WSN); Thermoelectric generator; ambient air; temperature of soil

ABSTRAK

Nod penderia wayarles (WSN) kini menjadi topik yang hangat disebabkan oleh aplikasinya yang meluas dalam beberapa jenis bidang seperti kesihatan, automasi, keselamatan dan lain-lain. Namun, WSN terutamanya di kawasan terpencil di mana penggunaannya adalah paling menguntungkan, dihalang oleh cabaran yang besar iaitu sumber tenaga yang terhad, kuasa bateri. Banyak alternatif telah dikaji untuk mengatasi masalah tersebut dan salah satu penyelesaiannya adalah penuaian tenaga menggunakan tenaga haba. Tenaga haba merupakan bekalan yang banyak dan mudah didapati di mana sahaja. Justeru, kajian ini mencadangkan satu konsep memanfaatkan peranti termoelektrik untuk menukar tenaga haba menjadi tenaga elektrik, dan juga kajian kebolehlaksanaan kaedah ini untuk menghidupkan WSN. Tapak kawasan yang dikaji adalah di sekitar tasik Fakulti Kejuruteraan dan Alam Bina (FKAB). Profil suhu tanah pada kedalaman yang berbeza telah dikaji untuk mencari kedalaman optimum untuk perbezaan suhu yang maksimum antara ambien dan di bawah tanah. Kecekapan penjana termoelektrik (TEG) telah diuji dengan beberapa jenis konfigurasi yang berbeza di makmal. Setelah itu, storan tenaga dan penukar langkah-naik digunakan untuk meningkatkan lagi kemampuan TEG. Kesemua komponen kemudian digabungkan dan diuji untuk menghidupkan beban DC mengikut profil suhu yang dikutip. Beban DC yang diuji adalah Arduino Uno, dan ia mampu dihidupkan untuk jangka masa yang pendek, sebelum tenaga habis sepenuhnya. Ringkasnya, penuaian tenaga haba dapat menghidupkan beban elektronik, namun ianya tidak cukup efisien untuk menjadi sumber bekalan tenaga yang tunggal.

Kata Kunci: Penuai Tenaga Haba; Nod penderia wayarles (WSN); Penjana Termoelektrik (TEG); suhu ambien; suhu tanah

INTRODUCTION

The usage of wireless sensors networks (WSNs) has been increasing over the years due to its potential to be applied in various fields such as medical, automation, monitoring and many more. However, the usage of WSNs is challenged particularly in remote areas due to its limited energy and lifespan (Engmann et al. 2018). The main aspect that affects the WSNs application is the energy source as the available energy influences the performance and lifespan of the system (Pullwitt et al. 2018). The usage of battery to supply a large network is not practical as it costs a lot especially in replacing battery and maintenance fees. Besides, battery has a finite capacity (Pop-Vadean et al. 2017).

Researchers has been coming up with alternative solutions to improve the lifespan of WSNs by reducing the overhead connections, duty cycle etc. A few algorithms have proven to improve the lifespan of the sensors in WSNs. However, energy harvesting remains one of the best alternatives. Energy harvesting, in facts, able to provide a reliable and in-situ energy source by converting ambient to electrical power (Moser et al. 2012). In contrast, energy harvesting also enables the deployment of new sensors system particularly in areas where wired infrastructure are not practical to be built (Mullen et al. 2015). A few different techniques for energy harvesting has been studied, for example, solar, wind, heat, vibration, etc. (Verma & Sharma 2019). This leads to the need to change from primary battery to secondary battery, and using the energy harvesting to charge and recharge the secondary battery.

One of the technologies that has been studied is the usage of energy from temperature difference between two objects. The ambient air becomes warm in daylight due to the solar radiation and becomes cold at night. This periodic changes in temperature of air will transfer to any objects in contact. The object's temperature variation is then dampened by the thermal inertia, therefore creating a temperature difference between ambient air and the object (Moser et al. 2012). Solid-state thermoelectric that utilizes Seebeck effect is considered to be efficient and reliable as it does not have any moving parts (Knight & Davidson 2010). A complete system of thermoelectric energy harvesting constitutes of an interface between the ambient air and soil, a thermoelectric generator (TEG), and an electronic load. The output of the energy harvesting system is based on the energy source as well as the harvesting component. By using TEG to enable self-powering WSNs, it can reduce the maintenance work and cost, indirectly reducing the environmental pollution caused by the side chemicals products from battery production.

The connection of multiple TEGs will be electrically in series, as have been suggested by (Siddiqui & Maurya 2017). This is because parallel connections of TEG will have lower voltage and higher currents, leading to I^2R or Joule heat losses. Afterall, the maximum power output for either series or parallel connections are almost similar (Chen et al. 2017). In fact, research by (Montecuccio et al. 2014) shown that the losses due to mismatch conditions is lowered in series connection.

One such application for thermal energy harvesting is using the temperature difference between ambient air and soil (Carvalhaes-Dias et al. 2018). TEG can harvest the solar heat radiation and the usage of heat sink in soil allows energy harvesting throughout day and night. As have been researched by (Pullwitt et al. 2018), the solar radiation accumulates a significant amount of heat in the soil, and taking soil thermal inertia into account, it could be a potential energy sources to power up WSNs. The sensors and devices could be powered up by secondary battery, operating at nominal voltage for a short amount of time, a few times a day.

The system design for the energy harvesting devices are quite straightforward. Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram representation. A heat sink is buried in the soil and a ceramic plate that is painted black is placed on top of TEG. During daytime, the ambient air is warmed up, heating the ceramic plate; the heat pipe will transfer the heat to the buried heat sink and be dispersed. This system shows an advantage during nighttime, as it is still able to generate energy due to inverted temperature profile; ambient becomes cool and soil becomes warm. Research by (Yildiz & Coogler 2017) has shown that the microscale TEG is capable of generating $15\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^3$ from temperature difference of 10°C .

FIGURE 1. Diagram of thermal energy harvesting (Carvalhaes-Dias et al. 2018)

According to (Nur et al. 2014), the nature as a whole are affected by different factors such as microclimate, built environment, topography, the plants, buildings, etc. Therefore, all these factors contribute to different temperature of ambient air.

Research by (Muhammad et al. 2016) at Gombak, Malaysia has shown that the deeper the depth of soil, the more constant the temperature as compared to ambient air. The data are shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. Temperature profile at Gombak (Nur et al. 2014)

Therefore, a study regarding temperature profile at UKM, Bangi, with a shallower depth will have to be conducted. This paper study the performance of TEG and test the reliability of the thermal energy harvesting system using temperature difference between ambient air and soil to power up WSNs.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology is split to three parts which are temperature collecting, lab assessment, and model integration.

Temperature Collecting

Arduino Uno and waterproof-temperature sensor DS18B20 are used to collect the temperature of the surface and in the soil of various depth at 10cm, 20cm and 30cm. The site that has been studied is at the lake nearby Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment (FKAB). Since WiFi utilities is not available in this area, thus data collected is not able to store in cloud. Therefore, Ethernet Shield V2.0 has been used to utilize the micro SD card slot to store the data collected. The data collected is then analyzed in computer and graph is plotted to analyze the relationship. This temperature collecting model is built inside a box to prevent the electronics component from water damage. The setup is as in Figure 3. Two situation that needs to be considered when using the box is that, the box needs to withstand rain, and stagnant water after the rain, or the level of lake water rises up after dusk. The box is sealed using plastic bags and hot glue gun; the box is placed on top of a chair.

FIGURE 3. Temperature collector model

The connection of Arduino Uno and DS18B20 is based on Figure 4, where the resistor works as pull-up resistor. Since this temperature collector model is deployed nearby the lake where there is not any power outlet available, two powerbanks are used alternately for keeping the model staying functional for a week. A fully charged 20000mAh powerbank can power up the model for 2 days straight.

FIGURE 4. Schematic connection

The timestamp for the model is set beforehand using laptop before deployed. The timestamp is obtained from <https://www.epochconverter.com/>, and the unit has to be converted as the count starts from 1st Jan 1970. Epoch is used as the reference point from where the time is counted. The timestamp process would have been easier if RTC DS3231 module had been used.

Lab assessment

Different methods of connecting multiple TEG affects the output of TEG. It can either be connect series or parallel, electrically or thermally. In this setup, the TEGs are connected electrically in series, and stacked up to study the effect of on the outcome. Data collected are then plotted onto graph for analysis to determine which configuration is the most suitable for this research. Besides, there many different types of TEG as well, of various sizes and materials, and it affects the output significantly.

Five variation of tests has been conducted using a total of three TEG with the model TEP1-12656-0.6 measuring 56mm x 56mm, to evaluate its performances. The tests are carried out as follow: (1) single TEG, (2) two TEG series, (3) three TEG series, (4) two TEG parallel and (5) three TEG parallel. The test is repeated using TEG model SP-1848, measuring 40mm x 40mm.

FIGURE 5. Different connections of TEG

The setup to test TEG is shown in Figure 6. TEG is placed onto the hot plate where thermocouple data logger TC-08 is used to monitor the temperature on both sides of TEG. Heat sink is then placed on top of TEG to improve the cooling effect and ease the heat flow.

FIGURE 6. Test setup for TEG testing

In order to manage and stabilize the voltage output supplied to electronics load, a demonstration circuit 1587 by Linear Technology is used. This board has a component LTC3105, a high efficiency step-up DC/DC, single polarity converter that can operate from input starting from 250mV, specially designed for low power application. The output of this board is stored in a super capacitor, which is then connected to another DC1587 board. The first DC board is used to step up the voltage, and second DC board is for regulating the voltage output.

FIGURE 7. Connection layout

The demonstration circuit board DC1587 has been tested to evaluate its performance as well, by supplying DC voltage. The stepped-up voltage from DC board is used to charge supercapacitor, and the time taken has been recorded. Two supercapacitors of 10F 2.5V each are connected in series to increase its voltage capacity to 5V.

Model Integration

After each component has been tested and evaluated, the components are then integrated to a fully functional system. Aluminum is used as the plate and heat pipe for its good thermal conductivity property and a widely available material. A heat insulator is used to wrap around the heat pipe, to prevent unnecessary heat loss and

to prevent unwanted heat from the soil to disturb it, indirectly improving the efficiency of heat transferring to heat sink. In addition, thermal paste is used to fill in the gaps between the components to maximize surface area in contact.

The top plate will absorb the heat energy, passed it to TEG and then dissipated to soil via heatsink. At the same time, there exists a temperature difference across TEG, hence generating voltage. Figure 8 shows the process flowchart.

FIGURE 8. Process flowchart

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal energy harvesting system has been built and tested to power up an electronic load which is Arduino Uno

Temperature Collecting

The temperature of surface and in soil by the lake of FKAB has been studied for 5 days of various depth at 10cm, 20cm and 30cm. From the graph plotted in Figure 9, it can be clearly seen that the deeper the depth of soil, the temperature becomes more stable. Therefore, it gives a bigger difference of temperature with surface temperature by reference. In fact, the depth of 10cm shows a similar temperature profile pattern as the surface of soil.

FIGURE 9. Temperature of soil of various depth

Table 1 summarize the data extracted from graph in Figure 9. The highest temperature recorded on the surface is 39 °C dan its lowest is 23.87 °C. It is clearly shown that with depth of

30cm able to give maximum differences with reference to the surface of soil. Figure 10 shows the absolute temperature difference.

FIGURE 10. Temperature differences with referenced to surface temperature

Theoretically speaking, the deeper the depth of soil, the more constant the temperature it is. During the peak temperature, 30cm gives the highest temperature difference. However, as comparison to average temperature difference throughout five days period, 20cm shows a better reading.

However, the data size collected is not enough to represent the average temperature profile in Malaysia. Besides, it was a sunny week during the process of collecting temperature; there has not been much rain.

	10cm	20cm	30cm	Surfaces
Highest temp (°C)	34.00	29.94	28.56	39.00
Lowest temp (°C)	25.87	26.75	27.31	23.87
ΔT when surfaces peak (°C)	7.32	10.38	11.25	
ΔT when surfaces at its lowest (°C)	2.63	3.81	3.94	
Average temperature difference (°C)	2.51	3.34	3.31	

Lab Assessment

The data collected based on five variations of test on the performance of TEG has been analyzed and plotted onto graph. Graph in Figure 11 showing the

TABLE 1. Comparison differences in temperature

voltage generated by series connection of TEG TEP-12656. It can be clearly seen that as the number of TEG in series connections increases, the

voltage generated increases linearly too. This shows the scaling properties of TEG.

FIGURE 11 Series Connection Performance Evaluation

Referring to Figure 12, the result obtained from parallel connection of TEG TEP-12656 are showing the opposite result. This is due to as TEG are stacked up, the heat dissipation become less

effective. The differences in temperature between two sides of a single TEG becomes lesser, leading to lower output.

FIGURE 12. Parallel Connection Performance Evaluation

Another interesting finding is that the voltage generated by the TEG during heating up and cooling down processes are different by a slight margin. However, it still exhibits a linear relationship between temperature and voltage generated. From Figure 13, voltage generated

during heating up is slightly more than during cooling down. One possible explanation is that the test is carried out using hotplate. During heating, heat can be supplied accordingly and quickly. However, during cooling, it requires time.

FIGURE 13. Performance Comparison between Heating and Cooling

The second type of TEG that has been tested is TEG model SP-1848, and the result is compared with TEP-12656 in Figure 14. It exhibits a similar characteristic as the previous model TEP-12656, series connection increases the total output whereas parallel connection reduces the total output. However, one observation that can be made

is that differences in TEG size affects the output as well. The bigger the TEG, the greater exposure of its sides to respective heat and ambient air, hence, generates higher output. As a result, TEP-12656 with series connections will be used as it will generate higher output.

FIGURE 14. Comparison TEG 12656 and TEG SP1848

To improve the efficiency of the TEG output, demonstration circuit 1587 has been used and its performances are tested in the lab. It needs at least 250mV for it to operate. However, this board is proven to be not the best choice of selection as DC1664 by Linear Technology is the preferred choice. It features LTC3109, an autopolarity, ultralow voltage step-up that can operate as low as 30mV regardless of polarity. DC1587 is the only component available now and thermal energy harvesting generates energy from both polarities, hence the proposed solution could

not perform as had been planned.

Two supercapacitors rating 10F 2.5V each are connected in series and time taken to fully charge it are recorded in Figure 15. 1V and 0.55V are used because average temperature during daytime and nighttime is about 8°C and 3.5°C where TEG generates 1V and 0.55V respectively. This is based on the depth of 30cm in the soil. From the result obtained, assuming the temperature stays constant during the daytime, it needs about 6.58 minutes on average to fully charge it to 5V. As for nighttime, it needs 27.19 minutes to fully

charge it. One of the minor problems faced is that when using DC generator to charge the supercapacitor, the value fluctuates a bit within

range of $\pm 0.2V$, therefore it might affect the actual time needed to fully charge.

FIGURE 15. Time Taken to Fully Charge Supercapacitor

Model Integration

A prototype model has been built as in Figure 16. There are a few weaknesses in this model. First, the aluminum is prone to rustiness when exposed to air and water over a long period of time. Besides, the electronics loads that are connected to the TEG circuit must be waterproof too, which in turn will increase the overall cost of the project.

FIGURE 16. Model Prototype

However, this model was unable to test practically due to lack of components such as DC1664 and the setup of Dragino Shield for wireless transmission of data, or for remote monitoring purposes. Besides, this model has yet to be waterproof. Lastly, it lacks the appropriate size of heat sink for efficient heat transmission and dissipation. Therefore, it has no points to test it until all the components are gathered. This model is built with reference to Figure 17, by (Carvalhaes-Dias et al. 2018)

FIGURE 17. Reference Model Prototype (Carvalhaes-Dias et al. 2018)

CONCLUSION

A thermal energy harvesting system based on temperature of ambient air and soil is built. This system can generate sufficient voltage based on the temperature profile that are collected, to power up Arduino Uno for a short period of time. Characteristics of TEG has been studied and due to its low efficiency, DC booster has been used to increase its output level. However, it is still not efficient enough to be a stand-alone power supply.

The advantage of this system is that it can harvest energy regardless of day or night as there will be temperature difference when the temperature profile switched. Of course, DC1664 featuring LTC3109 is needed to enable harvesting energy from both polarities. Water is still the weakness of this system as components can be easily damaged during rainy day if it is not covered properly.

There are a few suggestions to further improve this system. Firstly, load matching influences a lot on the output of TEG. Maximum

efficiency of TEG can be attained when total resistance of load is equal to internal resistance of TEG. Second, since the energy harvesting of thermal using TEG is very low, probably it can be integrated with different type of energy harvesting especially solar energy harvesting. A lot of studies have been made in solar-thermal hybrid energy harvesting. Lastly, the wiring and components should be waterproofed.

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